

Scaffolding Futures: Teaching Critical Engagement with LLMs for Foresight in Leisure Education

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Abstract: This paper reports on an educational approach designed by the authors that teaches students to critically engage with Large Language Models (LLMs) for future research in leisure domains. It explores how structured scaffolding techniques can transform LLM hallucinations from a limitation into a creative asset for foresight practice, while positioning students as responsible architects of AI-assisted futures exploration.

The methodology combines scaffolding techniques for LLM interaction with Bevolo and Draeger's approach to creative hallucination management in foresight practice. The paper presents a five-step prompting framework that guides students through systematic exploration of leisure futures, from setting contextual foundations to synthesizing coherent scenarios. This approach was implemented within a major generalist program about Leisure Futures in a workshop format where students generated individual "signals" to be clustered and mapped onto quadrants to identify emerging trends.

Preliminary results from trials with students demonstrate that the structured scaffolding approach enables them to direct LLM outputs more effectively. Rather than using simple, open-ended questions, students learned to analyze problems, deconstruct them, and engage with LLMs in a structured manner that gave them greater control over outcomes.

Practical Implications: The developed framework offers educators a practical and replicable model for teaching responsible AI usage while fostering critical thinking. The approach is particularly valuable for foresight, futures research, and design futures education, where creative exploration of future scenarios based on "signals" with future potential relevance is mission critical.

Keywords: AI-augmented foresight; constructive LLM hallucination; forward-looking design methods; prompt-scaffolding methodology; responsible GenAI facilitation; systematic futures inquiry.

1. Introduction

1.1. Reimagining LLM Limitations: The Transformative Potential of Hallucinations in Futures Education

With the public introduction of ChatGPT at the end of November 2022, Large Language Models (LLMs) have rapidly evolved into increasingly sophisticated tools that are reshaping educational approaches and research methodologies across

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disciplines (Berti et al., 2025; van Liempt & van Reijssen, 2024). These generative AI (GenAI) systems have grown not only in number but also in their complexity and capabilities. They demonstrate enhanced contextual understanding, reasoning abilities, and multimodal processing that were previously unimaginable (Berti et al., 2025; Huang et al., 2024). As these technologies become more embedded in educational contexts, they present both extraordinary opportunities and profound challenges for teaching and learning practices.

The integration of LLMs into education has sparked considerable debate about their appropriate roles and limitations. While these models offer unprecedented access to information and novel forms of engagement, they also exhibit significant shortcomings that require careful consideration. Chief among these limitations is their tendency to hallucinate, generating information that appears factual but is incorrect or entirely fabricated (Jiang et al., 2024; McKenna et al., 2023; Sahoo et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2024). Beyond hallucinations, LLMs contend with embedded biases that can reproduce and amplify social inequities (Gallegos et al., 2023; Sahoo et al., 2024). They also exhibit problematic overconfidence in presenting speculative content (Jiang et al., 2024) context window constraints, such as a limited number of tokens that can be used, that restrict complex reasoning (McKenna et al., 2023), and opacity in their decision-making processes that complicates verification (Zhao et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2024).

The intersection of LLMs and futures thinking presents an interesting paradox. The very technological limitations that undermine LLMs' reliability, particularly their tendency to hallucinate beyond known information (Xu et al., 2024)—May, as we will argue later in this paper, serve as creative assets in futures research, where imagination and speculation are essential components. This paper explores this counterintuitive possibility, examining how structured prompt-scaffolding techniques might transform LLM hallucinations from liabilities into valuable tools for foresight practice in leisure education contexts. Prompt-scaffolding techniques provide temporary support structures that guide learners through systematic LLM interactions they couldn't otherwise complete independently. Foresight in this paper is defined as "*a systematic, participatory, future-intelligence-gathering and medium-to-long term vision-building process aimed at present-day decisions and mobilizing joint actions*" (FOREN Network, 2001), distinguishing it from futures studies through its focus on supporting strategic decision-making processes (Bevolo, 2016).

By recasting any AI limitations as potential strengths within carefully designed educational frameworks, we propose a new approach. This approach not only acknowledges LLMs' constraints but strategically employs them to enhance students' futures literacy and critical engagement with emerging technologies. Critical engagement refers to students' awareness that LLMs base decisions on patterns rather than facts, requiring them to verify output validity rather than accepting it uncritically. This perspective aligns with broader educational goals of developing transformative competencies that prepare students to navigate complexity, reconcile tensions, and create new value in uncertain futures (OECD, 2018).

These limitations become particularly significant when considering the suggested educational shift toward developing futures literacy as envisioned already in 2012 by UNESCO (2025). UNESCO (2018, 2025) defines *Futures Literacy & Foresight* as the capacity to use the future to inform action in the present. As societal complexities increase and change accelerates, educational institutions are increasingly focusing on preparing students to navigate uncertainty and envision multiple possible futures (Menéndez-Alvarez-Hevia et al., 2022). This futures orientation is especially relevant in design education, where creative exploration of future trends and scenarios has formed since the early 2000s a cornerstone of innovation and strategic planning. As a trickle-down effect, futures thinking has moved from specialized courses, e.g., dedicated Master's programs at the University of Houston or Swinburne in Australia, to Futures Literacy courses and educational packages in both business-oriented (economic, technical, and applied) and liberal arts higher education. This paper reports on a repeatable approach designed as a component for a generalist semester in Leisure and Events Management (LEM), within a specialized academy in leisure and events in the Netherlands.

2. Purpose and Value Statement

This paper presents a structured educational approach for teaching students to critically engage with LLMs for future research in leisure domains. Building on Bevolo and Draeger's (2024) work with professionals, we adapt their five-step framework for educational contexts, demonstrating how structured scaffolding techniques can transform LLM hallucinations from limitations into creative assets. The methodology combines scaffolding techniques with deliberate hallucination management, guiding students through systematic exploration of leisure futures—from establishing contextual foundations to synthesizing coherent scenarios.

The significance of this approach extends beyond the immediate context of leisure education. By positioning students as responsible architects of AI-assisted futures exploration rather than passive consumers of AI outputs, the framework contributes to broader educational goals of developing critical thinking, technological fluency, and futures literacy. Preliminary results from our workshops suggest that this structured approach enables students to direct LLM outputs more effectively while developing transferable skills essential for navigating an increasingly AI-mediated professional landscape.

3. Bibliographic Review

3.1. Future Research Methodologies in Education

Future research methodologies have gained increasing prominence in education as institutions recognize the need to prepare students for rapidly changing and uncertain futures. These approaches aim to develop what UNESCO (2025) calls "Futures Literacy & Foresight"—the ability to better understand the role of the future in what we see and do. Rather than focusing on prediction, futures literacy emphasizes the capacity to imagine multiple futures, interpret emerging changes, and make informed decisions in the present (cf. Menéndez-Alvarez-Hevia et al., 2022).

The OECD Learning Compass 2030 framework identifies three transformative competencies critical for navigating complex futures: creating new value through innovation and creativity; reconciling tensions and dilemmas through critical thinking and perspective-taking; and taking responsibility through ethical agency (OECD, 2018). These competencies align closely with the skills required for effective LLM interaction, suggesting natural synergies between futures education and AI literacy.

Current futures pedagogies employ various methodologies, including scenario planning, back-casting, simulations, and narrative techniques like speculative storytelling (Menéndez-Alvarez-Hevia et al., 2022). These approaches share common elements with creative design processes that can also be used in leisure education, which is an economic oriented education to enterprise and business management in the leisure industries, where envisioning possible, probable and alternative futures to define a preferable projection of what will be next, might form a key component of business planning and innovation management. As always, in foresight and in design, critical thinking, or the ability to question assumptions, imagine alternatives, and systematically explore possibilities rather than simply extrapolating current trends, is highly appreciated.

The integration of these future methodologies with LLM interaction presents intriguing possibilities for education. As Blanchet (2023) notes, futures literacy supports critical reflection on dominant narratives about the future, positioning learners not as passive recipients but as agents of change. LLMs, with their ability to generate alternative perspectives and speculative scenarios based on prompts, could potentially serve as collaborators in this futures exploration process, particularly when guided through appropriate scaffolding techniques (Bevolo & Draeger, 2024; Draeger & Bevolo, 2025; van Liempt, 2025a).

3.2. Evolving Skills and Potential Risks for LLM Engagement in Futures Education

The integration of LLMs into educational settings demands a reconsideration of the skills students need to engage with these technologies effectively and responsibly. Current research highlights the shift from viewing AI tools as mere information providers to seeing them as partners in the learning process that require specific interaction approaches. Grassucci et al. (2025) emphasizes that LLMs should function as guides that help students explore problem-solving strategies rather than as sources of definitive answers. This perspective necessitates a critical mindset where students actively question and validate AI outputs instead of passively consuming them.

The core competencies required for successful LLM interaction extend beyond basic digital literacy. Peláez-Sánchez et al. (2024) caution that overreliance on GenAI risks diminishing students' critical capacities, emphasizing the need for instructional strategies that prioritize analytical engagement with AI-generated content. This points to a reiterated information literacy that is introduced by LLMs—particularly the ability to verify sources, recognize bias, and understand AI limitations—as fundamental to their responsible use by students (Grassucci et al., 2025; van Liempt, 2025a). Students, since November 2022, when ChatGPT was publicly introduced, have not had the advantage of growing up in a past where LLMs were not available and had to rely on having fewer tools available. Post-LLM students must develop discernment skills to distinguish between factual content and plausible-sounding fabrications, especially as LLMs continue to generate increasingly convincing but potentially inaccurate information.

According to both Federiakin et al., (2024) and Walter (2024), effective prompt engineering has emerged as a crucial skill in using LLMs for educational purposes. Prompting involves the precise articulation of a problem, its context, and the desired constraints to an AI assistant. Crafting such inputs well will also enhance LLM responsiveness and reliability (Xu et al., 2024a). Xu et al., (2024b) note that the quality of prompts directly influences the value of the responses received. Prompting as a skill encompasses not only technical aspects but also communicative ones—students must learn to articulate specific and contextual questions, iterate based on responses, and engage in dialogue-based learning with LLMs (Federiakin et al., 2024). The development of these communication skills with GenAI represents a significant shift in how students approach information gathering and processing (Cain, 2024; Lee & Palmer, 2025; Walter, 2024).

4. Key Problem: LLM Hallucinations and Their Educational Implications

The limitations of LLMs present significant challenges for educational applications while simultaneously opening unique pedagogical opportunities. Hallucination—the tendency to generate plausible but incorrect information—remains perhaps the most notable limitation. Xu et al., (2024b) argue that hallucination is not merely a technical flaw but an inherent characteristic of GenAI that cannot be eliminated. This creates tension in educational contexts, where factual accuracy is traditionally prioritized. The phenomenon forces educators to reconsider how to teach information verification and critical evaluation in an age where incorrect information can appear highly credible.

Beyond hallucination, LLMs exhibit other limitations that complicate their educational use. Jiang et al. (2024) highlight how these models can present hallucinated information with unwarranted confidence, even when they possess accurate knowledge, due to issues in their inference processes. This overconfidence potentially misleads students who may lack the expertise to recognize errors. Additionally, contextual memory constraints restrict LLMs' ability to handle complex reasoning tasks that require integration of multiple information sources or extended logical chains, precisely the higher-order thinking skills that education aims to develop (McKenna et al., 2023).

These limitations have motivated educators to explore structured approaches that acknowledge the constraints of AI tools while using them to enhance learning. Rather than trying to eliminate these inherent limitations, Bevolo and Draeger have begun exploring how they might be reframed as features within specific educational contexts, particularly those focused on creativity, speculation, and futures thinking (Bevolo & Draeger, 2024; Draeger & Bevolo, 2025).

5. Potential Solution: Scaffolding Approaches for Structured LLM Interaction

Prompt-scaffolding techniques—providing temporary support structures that enable learners to accomplish tasks they couldn't otherwise complete—have emerged as a promising approach for structured LLM interaction (PromptLayer, 2025; van Liempt, 2025a). Tian et al., (2024) propose a theory-guided scaffolding framework for LLM-enabled metaphor reasoning, demonstrating how carefully structured prompts can guide models toward more reliable and nuanced responses. This approach breaks down complex interactions into manageable components, providing students with explicit support that gradually diminishes as they develop competence.

The scaffolding concept applies effectively to LLM interaction because it acknowledges both the potential and limitations of these tools while positioning the human user as the guiding intelligence. As van Liempt (2025a) notes in his scaffolding framework, problems are typically complex and benefit from being broken into smaller pieces. By providing context to limit the freedom of the LLM and deconstructing problems into manageable components, users can guide AI systems toward more reliable and targeted outputs.

This scaffolded approach has particular relevance for futures research, where the goal is not necessarily to predict with certainty but to explore possibilities systematically. In Bevolo and Draeger (2024) and Draeger and Bevolo (2025) the authors demonstrate how scaffolding techniques can transform what would typically be considered LLM limitations into creative assets. Their five-step approach—setting foundations, building knowledge layers, embracing creative "hallucinations," critical analysis, and synthesis—provides a framework for using AI to explore possible futures of lighting design. This process demonstrates how a carefully structured dialogue with AI can create creative insights beyond what either human or machine might generate independently.

5.1. Synthesizing Perspectives: Reframing LLM Hallucinations in Futures Education

The literature review reveals relevant intersections between LLM limitations and future education methodologies. While traditional views frame hallucinations as problematic inaccuracies requiring mitigation (Jiang et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2024b), emerging scholarship by Bevolo and Draeger (Bevolo & Draeger, 2024; Draeger & Bevolo, 2025) reconceptualizes these tendencies as potential creative assets within futures exploration. This transforms what would typically be considered errors into valuable tools for divergent thinking and scenario development. This reframing aligns with established futures literacy approaches that emphasize developing capacities for creative speculation, systematic exploration of possibilities, and critical discernment between factual foundations and speculative projections (Menéndez-Alvarez-Hevia et al., 2022; UNESCO, 2018, 2025). The scaffolded approach to LLM interaction proposed by van Liempt (2025a) emerges from this intersection. It offers promising potential for developing what Draeger and Bevolo (2025) term "liminal thinking"—the ability to move fluidly between evidence-based foundations and speculative horizons while maintaining critical awareness of the boundary between them. This synthesis suggests that the skills required for effective LLM engagement in futures education—critical evaluation, structured prompting, and creative integration—parallel the transformative competencies identified as essential for navigating complex futures (OECD, 2018).

6. Research Focus and Question

Building on this synthesis of literature at the intersection of LLM limitations and futures education, this paper investigates the specific question:

How can structured prompt-scaffolding techniques transform LLM hallucinations from limitations into creative assets for futures exploration in Design Futures education?

This research question directly addresses the gap identified in existing scholarship—while researchers have explored both LLM hallucinations and futures literacy separately, few have systematically examined how educational frameworks might intentionally leverage these AI tendencies as creative resources for futures thinking. By focusing on leisure education contexts, this study provides a concrete application domain for testing the theoretical integration proposed above.

7. Methodological Framework: Integrating Scaffolding with Futures Exploration

7.1. Hybrid Foresight Methodology

As anticipated, this methodology was implemented through workshop sessions conducted with undergraduate students studying Leisure and Events at Breda University of Applied Sciences (Buas), a higher vocational education level (HBO), in the Netherlands. The workshops involved 99 participants (27 international, the rest Dutch), aged 19-25 years, enrolled in the second year of the Leisure and Event Management program. Each workshop session accommodated approximately 20 students, organized into teams of four to five members. These workshops represented the students' first systematic engagement with LLMs for futures research. We expected many students to have had prior casual experience with LLMs.

Each workshop lasted approximately three hours and was preceded by a preparatory presentation introducing key concepts of LLM operation, limitations, and responsible usage principles. Essentially, the presentation for the students by van Liempt (2025a). The workshops were conducted in classroom settings with students working on their devices. Students used various LLM platforms based on availability and personal preference, including Microsoft Copilot (predominantly, as it was accessible through institutional accounts), ChatGPT, Google Gemini, and Claude. This diversity of platforms, while not ideal for standardization, reflects the real-world technological landscape students will navigate professionally.

The overall methodology governing the semester included three key steps:

- The review of archetypical scenarios of Leisure Futures, as based on Jim Dator's 1979 synthesis of archetypical futures scenarios (Dator, 2002) supplemented by GenAI extensions into specific leisure domains;
- The adoption of a Quadrants Tool, whereby single manifestations of possible, probable, and preferable futures might be mapped, as based on archetypical scenarios, therefore connecting longer-term futures envisioning (scenarios) with shorter-term manifestations (signals) of potential futures in leisure.
- The structuring of manifestations into "signals" reported using "Leisure Cards," which were optimized for automated foresight purposes.

Students were provided with the above methodological elements to ground their work, as captured in a peer-reviewed publication by two of the authors of this paper (Bevolo & Draeger, 2024). Furthermore, in addition to the reference paper and its translation into the Dutch language, students were provided with clear formats and frameworks to report the findings of their future explorations. They also received 25 Leisure Cards generated using GenAI by the authors of this paper. The purpose was to combine individual generativity from each student, tasked with creating one specific "signal" of possible, probable, and preferable Leisure Futures, with the earlier automated "signals". Each student could also draw a second Leisure Card from the automated collection of signals. Therefore, in a team of five students, mapping on the Quadrants Tool might entail the critical revision and mutual positioning of five selected GenAI automated Leisure Cards, to be selected from a folder with 25 possibilities, with five individually generated cards through GenAI, as a novel contribution and personal perspective on Leisure Futures.

As anticipated, throughout the workshop, students documented their interactions with LLMs using a standardized template based on the "Leisure Card" format (Bevolo & Draeger, 2024). This template captured:

- Signal title and descriptor
- Key reference points justifying the signal
- Optimistic and pessimistic future trajectories
- Key uncertainties (DESTEP factors)

- Possible actions toward resilient outcomes
- A central question capturing the signal's essence

These structured outputs provided tangible artifacts for student reflection and instructor review, while forming the basis for the collective mapping exercise. The documentation process also created what we call "interaction transparency,"—making visible the dialogue between the student and LLM that produced the final outputs.

After completing the five-step process for individual signals, students were guided to place their signals on a collective mapping framework adapted from Bevolo & Draeger's (2024) Leisure Futures Quadrants. This mapping exercise converted individual "signals" into "clusters", according to Design Futures established methodologies (Bevolo, 2016), leading to theming, envisioning, and ultimately generating a team-based collective visualization of Leisure Futures.

By positioning their individual "signals" and a selection of automated "signals" as provided within this Quadrants Tool, students could identify emerging patterns, clusters, and tensions across the different futures explored by the class. This mapping exercise can be described as "collective sensemaking"—moving beyond individual insights to identify broader patterns in possible futures.

7.2. Core Methodology: The Five-Step Prompting Framework

This paper specifically reports on the repeatable methodology for prompt design that led to the creation of individual Leisure Cards, thereby focusing on a specific component of the overall futures research process. Such components were designed as a workshop format, for students to follow specific instructions after receiving frontal lectures about futures literacy, urban resilience as a general direction of preferable futures, and earlier applications of the overall methodology to lighting design futures, as a reliable example (Bevolo & Draeger, 2024). The prompt design and the prompting itself were instead novel in their design and might therefore be regarded as the most experimental part of the process.

The workshop structure followed a guided progression through the five-step framework, with instructors providing:

- Initial demonstration of each step
- Example prompts that students could adapt
- Real-time assistance with prompt refinement
- Periodic whole-group discussions of emerging insights and challenges

Students work individually; however, they do so in a team setting (see [Figure 1](#)) where each team has five team members for peer feedback and peer-to-peer guidance based on Train-the-Trainer earlier sessions, to explore distinct signals within the leisure domain, though peer consultation was encouraged during the critical analysis and synthesis phases.

Figure 1. Student Group Engagement During Workshop Session with Instructor Guidance (Edited Image).

The core of our repeatable prompting methodology is a structured five-step framework that progressively guides students from establishing foundational knowledge to synthesizing creative futures insights (see [Figure 2](#)). Each step involves

specific prompting strategies designed to elicit increasingly sophisticated responses from LLMs while maintaining student agency in the interaction. Below, we detail each step with example prompts and rationales.

7.2.1. Step 1: Setting the Foundation

In this initial step, students establish clear boundaries and contextual parameters for their exploration. Rather than asking broad, open-ended questions about leisure futures, students craft prompts that specify:

- The specific leisure domain being explored
- The time horizon (typically 25 years forward)
- The exact outputs requested (e.g., technologies, trends, signals)

This structured foundation serves two critical purposes: it provides the LLM with sufficient context to generate relevant responses, and it establishes clear expectations that help students critically evaluate the outputs they receive. An example of a foundation-setting prompt is provided in [Table 1](#).

The deliberate request for confirmation at the end illustrates what we identify as a “critical scaffold”—ensuring mutual understanding before proceeding to more complex interactions.

Table 1. Step 1: Foundation Setting: Example Prompt

Component	Content
Prompt	<p>I want to explore future signals for immersive technologies in the leisure industry over the next 25 years. Please help me by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifying 3-5 potential "signals" or emerging trends in immersive leisure experiences. 2. Creating a concise title for each signal. 3. Providing a one-line descriptor for each signal. 4. Suggesting areas where these signals might intersect with broader societal trends. <p>Before you generate scenarios, please confirm your understanding of these parameters.</p>

7.2.2. Step 2: Building Knowledge Layers

Once the foundation is established, students guide the LLM to systematically explore each area identified, building a reliable knowledge base before venturing into speculation. This step emphasizes factual accuracy and current evidence, helping students distinguish between what is known and what is speculative. [Table 2](#) illustrates a knowledge-building prompt that guides students through systematic evidence gathering.

Table 2. Step 2: Knowledge Building: Example Prompt

Component	Content
Prompt	<p>Let's focus on documenting the evidence for each immersive leisure signal you identified. For each signal:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify key references or evidence that justify this signal's relevance today. 2. Describe its current state in the leisure industry. 3. Identify its current limitations or implementation challenges. 4. Suggest why this signal is worth monitoring for future developments. <p>Please stick to the verified, current evidence in this step - we'll explore speculative ideas later.</p>

This step demonstrates the principle of "knowledge-first interaction"—establishing a shared understanding of existing knowledge before venturing into creative exploration.

7.2.3. Step 3: Embracing Creative "Hallucinations"

The third step represents (Table 3) a deliberate pivot from factual exploration to creative speculation. Here, students explicitly invite the LLM to generate more speculative content while maintaining a connection to the foundations established earlier. This step embodies the core insight from Bevolo and Draeger (2024)—that LLM tendencies toward hallucination can be deliberately harnessed for creative exploration in future contexts.

Table 3. Step 3: Creative Speculation: Example Prompt

Component	Content
Prompt	Based on the immersive leisure signals and evidence we discussed:
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> For each signal, describe in one sentence the most optimistic future development (preferably a positive outcome) in 2050. For each signal, describe in one sentence the most pessimistic future development (possible negative outcome) in 2050. Don't worry about complete feasibility but maintain a connection to the original signal.
	Feel free to be speculative and imaginative - we're exploring possible futures.

This approach aligns with what Draeger and Bevolo (2025) term "liminal thinking"—the deliberate suspension of disbelief to explore creative possibilities while maintaining awareness of the speculative nature of the exercise. This is a necessary skill for futures literacy to enable practitioners and participants to think about a range of future possibilities while remaining grounded in historical and present concerns. Liminal thinking applies to AI output, especially hallucinations, similarly. After thinking critically, participants can remain grounded in factual evidence while exploring what the implications of the output may mean for the future. If there are hallucinations, the question becomes: how could the hallucination become true over time? For biased statements that are AI-generated, practitioners and participants can think liminally about exploring the bias by assuming it is accurate while still maintaining a grounding in their perspectives.

Figure 2. Progression Framework from Evidence-Based Knowledge to Creative Speculation in the Five-Step Approach.

7.2.4. Step 4: Critical Analysis

In the fourth step, students apply analytical frameworks to the speculative futures generated in Step 3. This critical examination helps students identify key uncertainties, drivers of change, and potential implications without dismissing creative possibilities outright. The analytical framework approach is exemplified in [Table 4](#).

Table 4. Step 4: Critical Analysis: Example Prompt

Component	Content
Prompt	<p>For each immersive leisure signal and its potential futures:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify the most significant DESTEP factors (Demographic, economic, social, technological, environmental, and political) that are creating uncertainty for this signal. 2. Which of these factors would have the greatest impact on whether the optimistic or pessimistic future materializes? 3. Suggest one practical action or strategy to leverage this signal toward a preferable resilient outcome in society. <p>Let's analyse these even if some elements seem currently challenging to implement.</p>

This step exemplifies what we describe as "critical engagement with AI outputs". We encourage students to neither uncritically accept nor dismiss LLM-generated content but rather analyse it through established analytical frameworks.

7.2.5. Step 5: Synthesis and Integration

In the final step, students synthesize insights from previous steps into coherent, structured outputs. This integration process helps students transform fragmentary speculations into meaningful future narratives that connect to present action possibilities. [Table 5](#) provides an example of how students can synthesize insights from previous steps into coherent, structured outputs.

Table 5. Step 5: Synthesis and Integration: Example Prompt

Component	Content
Prompt	<p>Based on our discussions, for each immersive leisure signal, please:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Refine the signal title and descriptor to be clear and compelling. 2. Ensure we have credible reference points that justify the signal. 3. Confirm we have concise one-line descriptions for both optimistic and pessimistic futures. 4. Verify we've identified key DESTEP uncertainties that could affect outcomes. 5. Finalize a possible action that promotes resilience. 6. Formulate one key question that captures the essence of this signal to social resilience.

This final prompt demonstrates what we call "integrative scaffolding," guiding the synthesis of multiple elements into a coherent whole while prompting reflection on how the exploration connects to concrete action possibilities.

7.2. Ethical Considerations

While formal ethical guidelines were not explicitly implemented beyond the preparatory lecture on responsible AI usage, several ethical considerations informed the workshop design:

- **Transparency:** Students were required to maintain full documentation of their LLM interactions, ensuring that the process behind their insights remained visible and accountable.

- **Critical awareness:** The scaffolded approach emphasized critical evaluation of LLM outputs rather than uncritical acceptance, addressing concerns raised by Peláez-Sánchez et al. (2024) we share about diminishing critical capacities.
- **Attribution clarity:** The workshop emphasized the distinction between student-directed exploration (where students maintain intellectual ownership) and LLM-generated content (which requires appropriate attribution).
- **Bias awareness:** Students were encouraged to consider how their prompting choices and the LLMs' training biases might influence the futures being explored, particularly regarding cultural assumptions about leisure.
- These considerations promote "responsible GenAI engagement"—maintaining human agency and critical awareness while benefiting from AI capabilities (van Liempt, 2025a).

7.3. Limitations of the Methodological Approach

While our approach offers a structured framework for teaching students to engage with LLMs for futures exploration, several methodological limitations should be acknowledged:

- **Platform diversity:** The use of multiple LLM platforms created inconsistencies in student experiences, as different models demonstrate varying capabilities and tendencies toward hallucination.
- **Time constraints:** The three-hour workshop format limited the depth of exploration possible, particularly for the critical analysis and synthesis steps that require more reflective engagement.
- **Evaluation frameworks:** The methodology focused primarily on process guidance rather than outcome evaluation, leaving open questions about how to assess the quality and originality of student-LLM collaborative outputs.
- **Domain knowledge variance:** Students' varying backgrounds in leisure studies affected their ability to critically evaluate LLM outputs, suggesting that domain knowledge remains crucial even in AI-assisted exploration.

These limitations indicate areas for future methodological refinement, particularly regarding standardization of platforms, the development of evaluation frameworks, and integration with domain knowledge development.

7.4. Preliminary Findings

Preliminary findings from workshop implementations conducted on June 18, 2025, provide initial insights into student experiences with the structured scaffolding approach. Student feedback from Dutch workshop sessions revealed mixed but informative responses to the methodology.

Students demonstrated skill development in structured AI interaction, with participants noting they learned to "Chat [GPT] beter leren gebruiken" [use ChatGPT better] and experienced growth in "meer structuur creëren" [creating more structure] (Student feedback, personal communication, June 18, 2025). However, feedback also revealed tension between scaffolded guidance and creative autonomy. One student commented: "Ik vond copy-paste niet leerzaam (prompts). Ik was liever creatief uitgedaagd" [I didn't find copy-paste educational (prompts). I would have preferred to be creatively challenged].

These preliminary findings suggest the structured approach successfully develops AI interaction competencies while highlighting the need to balance guided learning with opportunities for independent prompt creation in future iterations.

8. Discussion and Conclusion

The methodology developed for this educational methodology combines two central approaches. These are structured scaffolding techniques for LLM interaction by van Liempt (2025a) and the creative hallucination management framework for futures exploration by Bevolo and Draeger (2024) and Draeger and Bevolo (2025). By synthesizing these approaches, we created a systematic yet flexible framework that guides students through increasingly complex interactions with LLMs while encouraging creative exploration of possible leisure futures.

This integrated approach responds to what we identify as the paradoxical nature of LLMs in educational settings—tools that simultaneously present limitations in factual reliability while offering extraordinary capabilities for ideation and exploration. Rather than attempting to eliminate these tensions, our methodology embraces them, recasting LLM limitations as potential assets within the context of futures research.

The central innovation of this approach lies in its structured progression—moving from highly bounded, factual inquiries toward increasingly speculative explorations as students develop both critical awareness of LLM limitations and creative capacity to direct these tools productively.

This work contributes to emerging discourse on generative AI in foresight, innovation, and design education by offering a repeatable approach for prompt writing and by reframing LLM hallucinations as potentially valuable creative assets when properly managed. The methodology provides a concrete framework for implementing this approach in the design of futures education, emphasizing student agency and responsibility in human-AI collaboration.

While recent research has made significant strides in understanding both LLM limitations and future education approaches, several notable gaps remain at their intersection. Although Bevolo and Draeger have pioneered the creative reframing of LLM hallucinations for professional futures exploration, their work has not been extended to educational contexts where students can learn and apply these techniques.

Most critically, there remains a methodological gap in how to structure educational experiences that position students not as passive recipients of AI outputs but as critical architects of AI-assisted futures research. This paper addresses these interconnected gaps by proposing a structured pedagogical approach that builds on existing foundations while creating a bridge between LLM limitations, scaffolding techniques, and futures literacy development in leisure education contexts.

Looking forward, maintaining a long-term vision that positions AI as a tool rather than a replacement for human capabilities will be essential for educational practice. Our approach is based on the idea that the most profound learning occurs when students are actively engaged with LLM outputs—questioning, refining, and extending the initial ideas through human creativity and critical thinking. This aligns with van Liempt and van Reijssen's (2024) caution against both utopian and dystopian visions of AI in leisure contexts, suggesting instead a balanced approach that recognizes AI as augmenting human potential rather than replacing it. By teaching students to transform LLM hallucinations into creative opportunities through structured scaffolding, we help ensure that GenAI remains a valuable tool for human thought rather than its replacement.

8.2. Future scope

While this paper has focused specifically on application within the field of leisure studies, the approach is transferable to other academic disciplines. The methodological framework for LLM interactions in futures thinking could readily be adapted for business education, environmental sciences, healthcare studies, or engineering programs (Malik et al., 2025; Niiniluoto, 2001). Each field benefits from structured exploration of potential futures, and the scaffolding techniques detailed in this paper provide a template that can be customized to different epistemological requirements. As van Liempt and van Reijssen (2024) suggest, the question of whether AI technologies will transform society in utopian or dystopian ways transcends disciplinary boundaries, creating a shared urgency for futures education across fields.

The pedagogical implications of this work extend to digital literacy development. As LLMs become increasingly prevalent in educational contexts, students require not only technical proficiency but also critical awareness of how these tools shape knowledge production. Our approach emphasizes the development of what might be termed "GenAI literacy"—the ability to effectively prompt, critically evaluate, and appropriately contextualize LLM-generated content. By structuring students' engagement with LLMs through scaffolding techniques, we provide opportunities to develop these crucial literacy skills while simultaneously advancing domain knowledge. This dual benefit represents a promising direction for pedagogical innovation that acknowledges the growing importance of critical GenAI engagement skills.

The educational literature on LLMs, in particular Grassucci et al. (2025) and Peláez-Sánchez et al. (2024), treats hallucination as a problem to be mitigated rather than a potential creative resource, especially in speculative domains such as design and leisure. By demonstrating how structured scaffolding can transform these apparent limitations into educational assets, this work opens new possibilities for responsible AI integration in future education across disciplines.

Author's Note on Uses of AI Tools

Regarding the use of AI and Large Language Models (LLMs) in this report, the authors practised what they preached in this paper. While AI is often seamlessly integrated into everyday tools like Word and Excel, this report acknowledges its contributions. Parts of the text were rewritten with the help of ChatGPT's 'Linguist Friend' by van Liempt (2025b), which improved spelling, grammar, and clarity while preserving the tone of the original text. Different AI and generative AI (GenAI) tools were also used for different purposes. Claude 3.7 Sonnet by Anthropic (2025) was used to structure the narrative and integrate sources. The AI-powered academic search engine, Semantic Scholar by Allen Institute for AI (2025) and the AI-powered conversational search engine Perplexity by Perplexity AI (2025) were used for finding relevant literature. Figures 1 and 2 were created by Adriaan van Liempt. Figure 1 was edited using AI generative features included in Adobe Photoshop 2025 (Adobe Inc., 2025) for anonymization purposes. Figure 2 was created using a combination of ChatGPT with DALL-E (OpenAI, 2025) Adobe Photoshop 2025 (Adobe Inc., 2025), and Gigapixel AI (Topaz Labs,

2025). Finally, it is important to stress that despite the use of AI and GenAI, the authors remain fully accountable for the content of the report they are responsible for.

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